

1 **Table S1.** Average uptake coefficients ($\times 10^{-7}$) at different periods for heterogeneous reaction of
2 NO_2 (10 ± 0.5 ppmv) with CaCO_3 as a function of RH (20, 40, 60 and 80%).

RH	20 %	40 %	60%	80%
0-3 h	1.04 ± 0.10	1.29 ± 0.08	0.96 ± 0.12	1.08 ± 0.26
3-6 h	1.40 ± 0.24	1.04 ± 0.28	1.12 ± 0.14	0.99 ± 0.80
6-12 h	0.83 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.04	0.93 ± 0.23	1.27 ± 0.64
12-18 h	1.27 ± 0.33	1.34 ± 0.28	1.43 ± 0.64	1.49 ± 0.52
18-24 h	0.78 ± 0.48	2.56 ± 1.11	0.51 ± 0.28	1.98 ± 1.09

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6 **Table S2.** Average uptake coefficients ($\times 10^{-7}$) at different periods for heterogeneous reaction of
7 NO_2 (2 ± 0.1 ppmv) with CaCO_3 as a function of RH (40 and 80%).

RH	40 %	80%
0-3 h	1.55 ± 0.19	1.38 ± 0.28
3-6 h	1.63 ± 0.60	0.57 ± 0.40
6-12 h	2.11 ± 0.26	1.16 ± 0.26
12-18 h	1.51 ± 0.99	1.02 ± 0.76
18-24 h	1.27 ± 0.65	1.56 ± 0.32

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11 **Table S3.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 12 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (10 ±0.5 ppmv) at 20% RH. The
 13 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 14 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalize mass of particulate water at 20%
 15 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 16 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 17 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.58 ±0.06)%	(1.35 ±0.13)%	(2.27 ±0.06)%	(3.67 ±0.36)%	(4.54 ±0.53)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	0.004 ±0.002	0.008 ±0.000	0.014 ±0.003	0.027 ±0.012	0.028 ±0.003
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.007 ±0.002	0.015 ±0.001	0.026 ±0.005	0.051 ±0.022	0.051 ±0.003
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.011 ±0.006	0.024 ±0.001	0.043 ±0.007	0.085 ±0.033	0.085 ±0.006
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.023 ±0.012	0.047 ±0.000	0.082 ±0.014	0.161 ±0.064	0.164 ±0.011
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.049 ±0.022	0.087 ±0.001	0.154 ±0.027	0.300 ±0.116	0.310 ±0.022

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21 **Table S4.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 22 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (10 ±0.5 ppmv) at 40% RH. The
 23 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 24 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalize mass of particulate water at 20%
 25 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 26 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 27 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.71 ±0.04)%	(1.29 ±0.16)%	(2.22 ±0.04)%	(3.69 ±0.31)%	(6.52 ±1.23)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	0.006 ±0.002	0.012 ±0.006	0.014 ±0.001	0.023 ±0.001	0.040 ±0.012
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.011 ±0.004	0.023 ±0.010	0.027 ±0.001	0.043 ±0.002	0.076 ±0.022
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.018 ±0.007	0.037 ±0.016	0.044 ±0.002	0.070 ±0.003	0.125 ±0.035
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.036 ±0.017	0.069 ±0.029	0.084 ±0.004	0.134 ±0.007	0.240 ±0.066
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.069 ±0.038	0.130 ±0.054	0.158 ±0.009	0.252 ±0.013	0.452 ±0.123

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31 **Table S5.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 32 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (10 ±0.5 ppmv) at 60% RH. The
 33 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 34 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalize mass of particulate water at 20%
 35 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 36 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 37 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.53 ±0.07)%	(1.15 ±0.08)%	(2.18 ±0.26)%	(3.76 ±0.71)%	(4.33 ±0.31)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	0.003 ±0.001	0.007 ±0.001	0.013 ±0.007	0.031 ±0.009	0.036 ±0.012
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.005 ±0.001	0.013 ±0.003	0.025 ±0.008	0.057 ±0.017	0.065 ±0.020
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.009 ±0.001	0.023 ±0.006	0.041 ±0.008	0.092 ±0.027	0.105 ±0.031
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.016 ±0.004	0.044 ±0.010	0.080 ±0.012	0.179 ±0.052	0.200 ±0.058
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.032 ±0.005	0.081 ±0.017	0.153 ±0.019	0.337 ±0.098	0.377 ±0.108

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41 **Table S6.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 42 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (10 ± 0.5 ppmv) at 80% RH. The
 43 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 44 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 20%
 45 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 46 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 47 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.60 ± 0.14)%	(1.15 ± 0.44)%	(2.55 ± 0.70)%	(4.19 ± 0.58)%	(6.38 ± 1.20)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	0.003 ± 0.001	0.007 ± 0.003	0.025 ± 0.014	0.025 ± 0.003	0.054 ± 0.014
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.006 ± 0.002	0.013 ± 0.005	0.049 ± 0.025	0.046 ± 0.006	0.100 ± 0.025
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.010 ± 0.002	0.023 ± 0.008	0.081 ± 0.039	0.074 ± 0.009	0.163 ± 0.040
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.018 ± 0.005	0.043 ± 0.015	0.155 ± 0.074	0.142 ± 0.016	0.312 ± 0.078
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.034 ± 0.009	0.079 ± 0.029	0.293 ± 0.137	0.267 ± 0.030	0.589 ± 0.149

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51 **Table S7.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 52 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (2 ±0.1 ppmv) at 40% RH. The
 53 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 54 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalize mass of particulate water at 20%
 55 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 56 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 57 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.17 ±0.02)%	(0.35 ±0.07)%	(0.82 ±0.06)%	(1.15 ±0.22)%	(1.43 ±0.14)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	0.001 ±0.001	0.002 ±0.001	0.005 ±0.000	0.007 ±0.001	0.010 ±0.002
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.001 ±0.001	0.005 ±0.002	0.010 ±0.002	0.013 ±0.002	0.019 ±0.003
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.002 ±0.001	0.008 ±0.002	0.016 ±0.001	0.021 ±0.004	0.031 ±0.006
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.004 ±0.001	0.014 ±0.003	0.029 ±0.001	0.042 ±0.007	0.059 ±0.010
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.008 ±0.002	0.023 ±0.003	0.052 ±0.002	0.076 ±0.013	0.108 ±0.017

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61 **Table S8.** Relative masses of nitrate and particulate water as a function of RH (20, 40, 60, 80 and
 62 90%) of CaCO₃ particles after heterogeneous reaction with NO₂ (2 ± 0.1 ppmv) at 80% RH. The
 63 masses of nitrate and particulate water are normalized to the initial mass of untreated CaCO₃:
 64 $m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$, normalized mass of nitrate; $m_w(20\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 20%
 65 RH; $m_w(40\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 40% RH; $m_w(60\%)/m_0$, normalized mass
 66 of particulate water at 60% RH; $m_w(80\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 80% RH;
 67 $m_w(90\%)/m_0$, normalized mass of particulate water at 90% RH.

time	3 h	6 h	12 h	18 h	24 h
$m(\text{NO}_3^-)/m_0$	(0.15 ± 0.03)%	(0.22 ± 0.04)%	(0.47 ± 0.06)%	(0.70 ± 0.17)%	(1.04 ± 0.07)%
$m_w(20\%)/m_0$	-	0.001 ± 0.000	0.003 ± 0.001	0.004 ± 0.001	0.007 ± 0.000
$m_w(40\%)/m_0$	0.001 ± 0.001	0.002 ± 0.001	0.006 ± 0.002	0.008 ± 0.002	0.012 ± 0.001
$m_w(60\%)/m_0$	0.004 ± 0.003	0.004 ± 0.002	0.009 ± 0.002	0.013 ± 0.004	0.023 ± 0.007
$m_w(80\%)/m_0$	0.007 ± 0.006	0.007 ± 0.001	0.018 ± 0.007	0.025 ± 0.007	0.046 ± 0.015
$m_w(90\%)/m_0$	0.010 ± 0.005	0.012 ± 0.000	0.034 ± 0.015	0.047 ± 0.013	0.082 ± 0.018

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